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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

KOZOKOV Sobirjon Zokirjonovich

*Namangan State University,
independent researcher*

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COVERAGE OF THE SOCIAL ASPECTS OF THE ENTREPRENEURIAL FACTOR IN MODERN INTERNATIONAL THEORETICAL CONCEPTS

ANNOTATION

The article analyzes the coverage of the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor in modern international theoretical concepts. In the article, the author focuses on the social views of Western and Russian sociologists, mainly the founder of the science of sociology O. From Conte's point of view, the sociologist of today has appealed to the theories of scientists. For this reason, the article attempts to study the concepts of entrepreneurship in terms of periods, highlighting the sociological views of prominent sociologists on entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial activity.

In addition, the article shows the factors influencing the formation and development of entrepreneurship, the role of well-known sociologists in society, their impact on stratification processes based on the views of scientists, and thus highlights their differences from other social groups.

Keywords: globalization, entrepreneurship, society, sociology, social solidarity, capitalist, property, income, social group, investor, stratification, Christianity, Protestantism, Calvinism, business ethics.

ОСВЕЩЕНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ АСПЕКТОВ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ФАКТОР СОВРЕМЕННОГО МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируется освещение социальных аспектов предпринимательского фактора в современных международных теоретических концепциях. В статье автор акцентирует внимание на социальных взглядах западных и российских социологов, главным образом основателя науки социологии О. С точки зрения Конте, современный социолог апеллирует к теориям ученых. По этой причине в статье предпринята попытка изучить концепции предпринимательства с точки зрения периодов, освещая социологические взгляды выдающихся социологов на предпринимательство и предпринимательскую активность.

Кроме того, в статье показаны факторы, влияющие на становление и развитие предпринимательства, роль известных социологов в обществе, их влияние на процессы стратификации, основанные на взглядах ученых, и, таким образом, подчеркиваются их отличия от других социальных групп.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, предпринимательство, общество, социология, социальная солидарность, капиталист, собственность, доход, социальная группа, инвестор, стратификация, христианство, протестантизм, кальвинизм, деловая этика.

TADBIRKORNING IJTIMOYIY JIHATLARINI YORITISH ZAMONAVIY XALQARO OMIL NAZARIY TUSHUNCHALAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada zamonaviy xalqaro nazariy tushunchalarda tadbirkorlik omilining ijtimoiy jihatlari yoritilishi tahlil qilingan. Maqolada muallif G'arb va Rossiya sotsiologlarining ijtimoiy qarashlariga, asosan sotsiologiya fanining asoschisi O. Konte nuqtai nazaridan, bugungi sotsiolog olimlarning nazariyalariga murojaat qilgan. Shu sababli, maqolada taniqli sotsiologlarning tadbirkorlik va tadbirkorlik faoliyati haqidagi sotsiologik qarashlari yoritilgan holda, tadbirkorlik tushunchalarini davrlar bo'yicha o'rganishga harakat qilinadi.

Bundan tashqari, maqolada tadbirkorlikning shakllanishi va rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar, taniqli sotsiologlarning jamiyatdagi o'rni, ularning olimlar qarashlari asosida tabaqalanish jarayonlariga ta'siri ko'rsatilgan va shu tariqa ularning boshqa ijtimoiy guruhlardan farqlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: globallashuv, tadbirkorlik, jamiyat, sotsiologiya, ijtimoiy birdamlik, kapitalistik, mulk, daromad, ijtimoiy guruh, investor, tabaqalanish, xristianlik, protestantizm, kalvinizm, biznes etikasi.

INTRODUCTION

In the process of globalization, entrepreneurship is a complex phenomenon with a complex structure that has attracted the attention of researchers in various fields of modern science and has become the object of research. Therefore, due to the lack of a clear definition of the concept of "entrepreneurship" to date, there is no scientific approach that would allow a full study of this phenomenon. This is because the sociologists who defined the concept of "entrepreneurship" approached it from their own point of view. This requires, on the one hand, the development of new theoretical directions in the study of entrepreneurship, and, on the other hand, entrepreneurship is a constantly changing process. This is because new areas of entrepreneurship are emerging as a result of changing needs of community members. The emergence of new areas of entrepreneurship is not only related to the needs of society, but also to the development of science and technology.

The purpose of studying the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor in modern international theoretical concepts is to study and apply foreign experience in our social life in the context of reforms in our country. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev's decree PF-5667 dated February 22, 2019 "On measures to support the conduct of sociological research" [1] provides for the establishment of cooperation with foreign sociologists in the development of sociological knowledge. In other words, the decree pays special attention to "membership in the International Association of Sociologists, participation in world sociological congresses and forums." This means that Uzbekistan will rely on foreign experience in the organization of research in the field of sociology, and on this basis it is planned to implement reforms.

HISTORY

Early concepts of entrepreneurship also paid special attention to the coverage of its social aspects, which can be seen primarily in the social views of Greek and Chinese philosophers, who were the hearths of ancient civilization.

The ancient Greek philosopher Plato (427-347 BC) was critical of entrepreneurship in his social views, and thus he condemned entrepreneurship. According to Plato, in an ideal state designed to control the members of society, the thirst for the purchase of silver and gold, the respect for it, disturbs the peace and order of the citizens.

Followers of Plato's ethics today regard private business and entrepreneurship as "inevitable evil" and associate it with its core idea, which is that "the state should provide its citizens with what they need" [2].

Aristotle (384-322 BC), a student of Plato, also paid special attention to entrepreneurship in his social views. Aristotle was one of the first to demonstrate an entrepreneurial strategy, such as the establishment of a monopoly, and gave concrete examples in this regard [2].

Based on the views of Plato and Aristotle, the views of ancient Roman writers and philosophers (Varro, Cicero, Seneca, etc.) on entrepreneurship are characterized by a purely pragmatic nature. They placed great emphasis on property, which played a crucial role in economic life. Property was conceived primarily as a legal concept and precedent associated with it in the execution of acts of purchase and sale, which served the development of Roman law.

Ancient Chinese thinkers elucidated more behavioral issues in the teachings of Confucius (551-479 BC). Because his teachings focused on intergenerational succession, that is, they had for centuries been subject to rules of conduct based on respect for elders and sovereignty, the older generation was entrusted with one responsibility: to manage and educate people.

He also described the duties of all groups of society in the teachings of Confucius. According to him, the peasants were shown preparing tools for field work, plowing, planting and harvesting crops, leading rulers, warriors, and so on. At the same time, Confucius reveals the mechanism of the market in his views, and in his view, "The market is the regulator of everything. Therefore, if everything is cheap, then there will be no surplus." [2] It is clear from this that Confucius understood entrepreneurship to mean the regulation of markets primarily through trade.

The social views of scientists of the ancient world serve as the basis for the creation of modern concepts of entrepreneurship.

PURPOSE

Therefore, the purpose of the study is to provide a scientific analysis of the coverage of the social aspects of modern concepts of entrepreneurship. The reason is that almost all modern sociologists have their own views on entrepreneurship, covering the social aspects of entrepreneurship. It is highlighted that these views have a place in the development of the economic life of society.

MISSION

The relevance of the study of the coverage of the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor in modern international theoretical concepts is characterized by a number of objective reasons. First, the fact that the creation of concepts of entrepreneurship has played an important role in all periods of human development calls for its study. Second, the research results serve as a theoretical and practical basis for the development of sociological theories about entrepreneurship. Thirdly, the analysis of theoretical concepts of entrepreneurship in the framework of the study will allow to study the social aspects of entrepreneurship in the period of reforms in the country, to identify promising areas of socio-economic processes in Uzbekistan.

RESULTS

The study of the concept of "entrepreneurship" in the field of sociology emerged only after the formation of "Sociology" as a separate discipline. The founder of sociology, O. Conte found that the economic activity of members of society depends not only on economic laws, but also on the laws of social life, the psychological factors that ensure social solidarity. For this reason, after the emergence of sociology as a science, the concept of entrepreneurship began to receive social attention. This is because the role of entrepreneurship in the life of society, the role of the entrepreneur in the social life is highlighted through the role of the individual in socialization.

German classical economist and theorist K. In his works, Marx expressed his views on entrepreneurial activity. K. Marx's Capital (Vol. 1, 1867) plays a major role in the study of the economic function of the entrepreneur as a capitalist.

Therefore, he argues that the development of entrepreneurial activity depends on the socio-economic and political problems of society. K. Marx did not consider entrepreneurship as a separate social group in his Marxist theory, because in his view, the entrepreneur represents the attitude to the means of production, not the criteria of this or that class, that is, the signs of psychological or social nature. For this reason, K. Marx compared the entrepreneur to the capitalist. When he said entrepreneur, he saw a capitalist who exploited the working class and made a profit using his own capital. He gave a clear definition of the concepts of income, profit, compared to other economists. In his view, entrepreneurship means unpaid labor to hired workers. K. The basis of Marx's economic teachings is the duality of goods. These are: the value of goods that meet certain needs and the value of goods as expressed in monetary terms. This is because in Marx's works, workers were employed by entrepreneurs and treated as wages, the object of the exploitation of workers. For this reason, his theories focused on property relations, and through this he put the interests of the workers first.

Also, K. Marx describes the attitude of the capitalist-entrepreneur to the methods of earning income, its size and the factors that limit it in the desire to enrich, and concludes: "Capital avoids noise and abuse, and is distinguished by its terrible nature. That is a fact, but it is not the whole truth. Just as nature is afraid of space, so capital is afraid of no profit. But when you have enough income, you have a lot of capital" [4, P.770.].

According to Karl Marx, the peculiarity of such a critical concept of business is the extreme position, because he sees any desire of an entrepreneur to make a profit as the realization of personal, narrow-minded interests that know neither the law nor the rules of ethics. On the other hand, there is truth in these ideas because when entrepreneurs are eager to make a profit, they stop thinking about the price for the personal success of the people around them or the success of the business.

K. Marx's ideological follower F. Engles also expressed his views on entrepreneurial activity, pointing to two main forms of capitalist income as profit:

The first is: entrepreneurial income (representing the capitalist as the organizer of surplus production);

Second: interest in capital (indicating it as the owner of the most important factors of production).

In addition, F. In his views, Engles emphasizes entrepreneurship as an important source of economic prosperity. At the same time, the entrepreneur creates cash flow, attracts investors, pays taxes. Entrepreneurship creates additional jobs, innovative products, increases the competitiveness of the country.

Russian-American sociologist P.Sorokin also made a sociological analysis of entrepreneurship in his views, and his concept of entrepreneurship was similar to that of Marx. In his sociological views, he defines the place of entrepreneurship in the system of social relations in terms of the theory of stratification. Entrepreneur is an economically independent owner, whose activity is the direct organization of entrepreneurship and control of employees. According to Sorokin, an entrepreneur should be distinguished not only from the property owner, but also from directors, managers, members of the corporation's board of directors, and employees [5, P.359]. It is obvious that Sorokin's ideas about the entrepreneurial layer emphasize his place in the social structure of society.

Representatives of the German School of Sociology also play an important role in covering the social aspects of entrepreneurship. German classical sociologist M. Weber has made the greatest contribution to the history of the development of sociological thought, including the development of ideas of economic sociology. Including u, O. Conte and E. Like Durkheim, he believed that the economic life of nations depended not only on their own laws, but also on specific socio-cultural factors. M. Weber's most important achievement is that he offers a detailed concept of providing various types of economic activity in a cultural context. In Protestant Ethics and the Spirit of Capitalism, M. Weber led a certain type of Protestantism (followers of the Calvinism-Protestant Church) to the formation of a new entrepreneurial ethic, which in turn developed a rational form of capitalism.

M. Weber's views on economics and entrepreneurship were echoed by another representative of German classical sociology, Wm. Zombart continued. V. In their works, Zombart and M. Weber highlight the problems of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial function. Because these thinkers have studied entrepreneurship from a social and market perspective and have studied economic relations through cultural relations.

In the views of M. Weber and V. Zombart, modern capitalism is manifested as a cultural-historical integrity, a form in which the whole meaning of modern European life, the whole meaning of life, is fixed. According to M. Weber, modern capitalism is a "terrible space" that enters the orbit, educates and creates the necessary economic entities, regardless of the dreams and aspirations of all people [6, P.76] is. M. Weber puts forward the idea that this unity is formed by a combination of religious, cultural, economic and political factors.

V. Zombart distinguishes two components of the capitalist spirit: the "entrepreneurial spirit" and the Palestinian, "burger (or civic) spirit". The first is manifested in the following characteristics of entrepreneurial character: willingness to take risks, perseverance, innovation, organizational skills, but at the same time the entrepreneur works as a winner and trader. Second, the burger spirit is the basis of the conservative nature of the entrepreneur, which is characterized by "traditional bourgeois qualities". These are: temperance, caution, manifested in emotional behavior. V. Zombart is based on the idea that the origins and causes of the capitalist spirit, the characteristics of the formation of its various components, stem from differences in the nature of these constituent elements [7, P.190].

It can be seen that M. Weber and W. Zombart may have paid special attention to the Protestant ethics of Christianity in covering the social aspects of entrepreneurial activity.

The famous American sociologist T. In his works, Parsons argues that those who engage in entrepreneurial activity, on the one hand, have social-acceptable and socially defined forms of personality-individual aspirations and their content in social action. On the other hand, in turn, it is related to the value-normative categories of culture, through which "... provides norms of selection and regulation of people in society" [8, P.453].

T. Parsons sees entrepreneurship as an integral part of the social systems that operate in society. Therefore, he sees the activity of an entrepreneur as a product of individual labor. Entrepreneurship is the product of existing values, norms and rules in the social system. This creates social stability in the society and ensures social development.

One of the most prominent representatives of modern sociology is E.J. Giddens also created his own concept, focusing on highlighting the social aspects of entrepreneurship. In his view, "Classes are related to economic inequalities between groups of people, which are related to the inequality of property and the conflict between material resources. We classes have a significant impact on lifestyle as large groups of people who differ in their overall economic opportunities. Your wealth and profession are the basis of the differences between the classes" [9, P.22].

E.. Giddens separates the resources of modern capitalist production. He divides these resources into three types of economic resources:

1. Investment or monetary capital management.
2. Management of means of physical production - enterprises, offices, etc.
3. Control over labor and power.

American sociologist E. Wright and E. In a society like Giddens's, it distinguishes attitudes toward different types of property as a feature that shapes the basic class, thereby minimizing all class differences in economic composition.

The economic disparities that have arisen in the process of globalization are mainly related to the inequality of property ownership and material resource management. E.. Wright and E. Giddens distinguishes two main classes of owners in modern capitalist society. These are:

- upper class;
- people deprived of property - emphasize the existence of workers or the lower class.

Also, E. Giddens's conclusion that the increase or absence of wealth is the main basis of class distinctions with the content of labor activity is valid, and his views on K. Consistent with Marx's concept. In conclusion, the above points can be noted that we have a large and stable position in society, as well as the main economic criteria that distinguish them from other social groups: ownership or disposal of property, profits from exchange as the main source of activity and income, etc. . For this reason, the entrepreneurial layer is the basic class of modern society. Like any social class, entrepreneurs reveal their essence through a certain characteristic activity. This requires the identification of specific features of entrepreneurial activity, indicating its specific features and types. Therefore, any socio-economic system based on certain property relations and, accordingly, a certain type of economic relations, also implies an appropriate type of labor activity.

Naturally, in such circumstances, the above are not the only conditions for the organization of entrepreneurial activity, but the class of entrepreneurs who determine the fundamental direction of development of society, which ultimately determines the mode of production of material goods and all forms of human life .

E.. Giddens describes entrepreneurial activity as a socio-economic phenomenon that characterizes the activities of people in the context of the development of market relations or the transition to the market. It is in the period of social development that entrepreneurship becomes the activity that determines the movement of people, and entrepreneurs become the main class that makes up this society.

Entrepreneurship has been sociologically studied not only by leading scientists of developed western countries, but also by leading sociologists of Russia. This is because the special attention paid to the study of entrepreneurial activity in the context of sociological research has determined the place and role of entrepreneurship in society. In addition, the sociological study of entrepreneurial activity determines the social structure of entrepreneurial activity, the status of entrepreneurs. Russian sociologist, academician T.I. Zaslavskaya studied entrepreneurship in a sociological way, which determines that entrepreneurship should be considered as an activity that is the basis for the emergence and development of the relevant social stratum. The structural features of this type of activity are:

- Profit planning;
- Freedom and autonomy of economic decision-making;
- Independence expressed by personal risk and personal responsibility [10, P.5].

T.I. Zaslavskaya offers an interpretation of the concept of entrepreneurship in a broad and narrow sense. The term "entrepreneurship" should mean the "core" group of the business community - the owners who run their own businesses. ... This group has all the hallmarks of entrepreneurship, it is professionally engaged in "making money", manages its capital independently, makes economic decisions independently, which in turn creates the basis for calling them classic entrepreneurs. At the same time, we propose to introduce a common notion that unites all Russians, to a certain extent, entrepreneurs, or, in other words, from classical entrepreneurs to hired workers who try to "make money" in their spare time. This layer covers the total number of subjects of production, commercial or financial activity, which are carried out independently on the basis of decision-making and for profit ... ” [10, P.7].

Thus, T.I. Zaslavskaya suggests the following classifications in determining the layer of entrepreneurs:

Entrepreneurs are mainly private owners of small enterprises and firms, who manage these activities themselves, without merging them with employment.

Self-employment are individuals who are engaged in the smallest business using the means of personal production, who are mainly qualified professionals and workers.

Business managers - hiring employees for management, mainly directors for small and medium enterprises, joint stock companies and the private sector, which are united to expand their business activities.

Semi-entrepreneurs are those who do not perform management functions and combine the main work with different types of business. These mainly include stock and private sector employees [10, P.10].

Also, academic T.I. Zaslavskaya conducted a number of sociological studies on gender issues in entrepreneurship, the problems of socio-psychological, socio-cultural characteristics of young business circles in the social structure of society in the social coverage of entrepreneurial activity. In particular, the role of entrepreneurship in the transformation of modern Russian society was studied. Because, T.I. Zaslavskaya sees the future of society directly in entrepreneurial activity.

Another well-known Russian sociologist and economist, V.V., was the first in Russia to study the social aspects of entrepreneurship from the point of view of economic sociology. Radaev is. In his early works on entrepreneurship, he considers this socio-economic phenomenon as the result of the emergence of a new social force in Russian society, and he studies their socio-psychological and cultural characteristics. In his views, he suggests a study through the economic function of entrepreneurship. V.V. Radaev in his work "Economic Sociology" gives the following general definition of entrepreneurship: "it is a type of activity that consists of the implementation of organizational innovations to obtain monetary income (or other additional income)" [11, P.204].

In addition, it highlights three important elements that make up a business. These include:

- The organization, as an object of action, independently separates the entrepreneur from the workers;
- The introduction of innovations helps to distinguish the entrepreneur from the manager and the tenant, the speculator and the intermediary;
- Cash income allows you to determine the success or failure of a business project.

At the same time, organizational innovations can be achieved through the creation of innovations, as well as the qualitative transformation of existing enterprises - their division and merger; renewal of property; radical changes in organizational structure [11, P.205].

Also, V.V. Radaev defines earning cash as a key feature of entrepreneurial activity. This is because the money earned by the entrepreneur as income can, of course, run out on its own. For this reason, entrepreneurs often spend their earned income on completely different goals, such as public image, the realization of great ideas, and education. This means that V.V. According to Radaev, behind any economic reasons, social relations are hidden [12, P.7] puts forward the idea.

In addition, V.V. Radaev organized the entrepreneurial activity and divided the needs for its development into four groups:

1. The need for survival, the desire to achieve minimal stability in the face of external challenges, to strengthen their position in the world and society, to achieve a stable standard of living, to gain confidence in the future;
2. Gdonistic needs, achieving maximum well-being, maximizing personal consumption and minimizing one's actions, etc .;
3. The need for social self-affirmation The desire to have a strong position in a particular social group;
4. The need for work, the pursuit of professional creative self-realization, the testing of innovation, the diversity of tasks, the danger and the food of success, the testing of professional ability, knowledge, skills, and so on.

Another Russian sociologist, A.V., who covered the social aspects of entrepreneurship. Bezgodov, in his sociological views, analyzed the nature and socio-economic functions of entrepreneurship in Russian society in the context of globalization. A.V. Bezgodov's sociological views "Essays on the sociology of entrepreneurship" [13, P.224] is reflected in his work, in which happiness in entrepreneurial work is defined by its main features such as innovation and profit. At the same time, he emphasizes that this economic phenomenon should be considered taking into account the ethical components of the entrepreneur's behavior and activities.

Consequently, A.V. Bezgodov understood that "entrepreneurship is an innovation that is accepted in a certain historical situation, within business standards, focused on making a profit, active in making money, systematic, independent and responsible."

Also, A.V. Bezgodov defined entrepreneurship as a social association and, through relevant empirical research, created a comprehensive socio-political portrait of Russian entrepreneurs, revealing the degree and mechanisms of their integration into social groups. It is a network of complex relationships between the millions of businesses and entrepreneurs that make up the structure and mechanisms of the microeconomy. At the same time, the entrepreneur should not be afraid of problems and not ashamed to solve them, look for ways and means to solve it - this is a characteristic feature of the entrepreneur's future. As a result, the entrepreneur is an energetic and strong-willed person, an organizer, an innovator, an economical and thrifty property owner.

Thus, A.V. According to Bezgodov, entrepreneurship is not only related to the formation and use of capital, but also a specific type of economic activity, which is a specific type and style of behavior, that is, includes the thinking, interests and culture of the individual. At the same time, the entrepreneur is called to ensure the necessary combination of personal interests with the public interest in order to benefit the individual in his activities. This is a basic requirement for a person engaged in entrepreneurial activity.

Another Russian sociologist, A. Ageev studied entrepreneurship in his research, and his views on entrepreneurship were developed by the Austrian-American scientist Y. It was close to Shumpeter's concept. In particular, it establishes the concept of entrepreneurship as a sign of innovation and emphasizes organizational innovation based on economic freedom as a key criterion of entrepreneurship. On this basis, A. Ageev attributes entrepreneurship to risk, independent decision-making, resource ownership, leadership, and so on.

V. Poznyakov is another Russian scientist who has studied the sociological aspects of entrepreneurship. His sociological concept P. Sorokin and Y. Consistent with Shumpeter's views, A.D. According to Poznyakov, entrepreneurs are people who only own property (capital, resources, means of production) and use hired labor to profit. At the same time, V. Poznyakov emphasizes that the innovative nature of entrepreneurial activity is not an important feature of it, but a necessary condition for the success of business [14, P.15].

In addition, V. Poznyakov considers property ownership as the main criterion of entrepreneurial activity. According to him, this criterion also distinguishes the group of workers from the entrepreneurs.

CONCLUSION

The above considered the level of coverage of the social aspects of entrepreneurship in modern concepts put forward by sociologists of developed countries. Indeed, since the dawn of human society, entrepreneurial activity has been practiced in every society, and it has been refined and developed over the centuries. For this reason, the concept of entrepreneurship has also been defined by philosophers of each period, highlighting its role in the life of society. Therefore, to date, the concept of entrepreneurship has not been clearly defined, and the concepts about it are also reflected in the social environment of its time.

It is well known that the concepts of modern sociologists are based on the concepts of philosophers who created before them, because scientists of the past created sociological concepts about entrepreneurship that allow them to analyze in a comprehensive way and differ from other social groups. However, the purpose of all these concepts is the same and serves for the development of entrepreneurial activity in society, the problems it faces, the formation of interpersonal relationships between social groups and the development of other factors.

Based on the above conclusions, we found it necessary to make the following suggestions and comments on the study of the coverage of the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor in modern international theoretical concepts:

1. In the study of the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor in modern international theoretical concepts, they should be considered as universal values. The reason is that the author of each concept is created from the point of view of the period in which he lived, and we have the opportunity to get a complete picture of the social environment of the society of that period. This requires the study of the concepts as they are created.

2. An objective study of the concepts of entrepreneurship created in the XIX-XX centuries will be the basis for the development of modern sociology. The reason is that in this period sociology is now a newly formed period, the basic concepts, categories and functions of the science of sociology have been formed.

3. In the coverage of the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor in modern international theoretical concepts, it is expedient to study the theories of scientists who have lived and worked in the history of mankind. Because it ensures intergenerational scientific succession in the creation of new entrepreneurial concepts. It is well known that in today's globalized world community, ensuring intergenerational succession is important, and through this it is possible to pass on to future generations the concepts of entrepreneurship created in the past.

4. In the study of the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor in modern international theoretical concepts, each nation must derive its own national character. Because every nation has its own national values, which must be respected on a regular basis.

5. In modern international theoretical concepts, it is expedient to use the results of the study of the social aspects of the entrepreneurial factor, first of all, in the management of the state and society. This is because in every society that is transitioning to market relations, entrepreneurship plays a key role and plays an important role in improving economic life.

In general, the coverage of social aspects of entrepreneurship in modern concepts in foreign developed countries is directly related to the development of society. Therefore, the introduction of these concepts in developing countries, where entrepreneurial activity is now, will certainly have a positive effect. That is, it will be the basis for the creation of entrepreneurial concepts in these countries, and thus create the basis for the development of entrepreneurial sociology as a science.

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Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55

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